

Physico-Chemical Study of the Reaction between Picolines and Chromithiocyanate

M. P. Gupta and M. L. Anand*

Pyridine and methyl substituted pyridines (α -, β - and γ -picolines) react with potassium chromithiocyanate in presence of acetic acid to yield stable light pink to dark violet-pink coloured compounds. The composition of these compounds has been determined.

Niels Bjerrum¹ observed the formation of the compounds between organic tertiary bases and chromithiocyanates. In many cases he observed variability in composition. Grossman² said that complexes derived from Al, Cr, Fe, Bi and V and SCN are all hexa-acid salts. But Scagliarini and Tartanini³ obtained lilac crystals of a mixture of hexamethylene tetramine aquo chromipentathiocyanate $(C_6H_{14}N_4H)_x [Cr (SCN)_5 \cdot H_2O] H_2O$ and chromihexathiocyanate $(C_6H_{14}N_4H)_3 [Cr (SCN)_6]$ when a solution of ammonium chromithiocyanate was treated with hexamethylenetetramine sulphate. Dubeky and Wangerhofer⁴ prepared some compounds reacting with pyridine and complex thiocyanates. In this communication the conductometric method has been applied and the variation in optical density has also been measured in case of pyridine and γ -picoline compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium chromithiocyanate was prepared and standardised by methods adopted by Roesler⁵ and Bjerrum¹. Pure pyridine and picolines (B.D.H.) were redistilled and stock solutions of M,3 were prepared in each case in a 200-ml volumetric flask containing 15 ml of acetic acid of sp. gr. 1.05 at 25°. Solutions of different concentrations were prepared by dilution with conductivity water.

The conductivity was measured by Sorfaas Conductivity Bridge Model RCM 15 BI, at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The difference in specific conductance against the fraction $\{[Cr (SCN)_6^{3-}] + [\text{organic base}]\}$ was plotted. Similar curves have been obtained. In case of pyridine curves A to C have been drawn in Fig. 1. Other plots have been omitted for economy of space. Using equimolar solutions (M/10, M/20 and M/50) each of organic bases and potassium chromithiocyanate, the stoichiometry of the compounds formed comes to 3:1.

*Present address: Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

1. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*; 1921, 118, 131.
2. *Ibid.*, 37, 442.
3. *Gazz. chim. ital.*; 1925, 55, 139.
4. *Chem. Abstr.*; 1940, 15, 217; *Chem. Zentr.*; 1941, I, 3199.
5. *Analyst.*, 1867, 141, 185.

Pyridine chromithiocyanate:—After the addition of pyridine in dilute acetic acid to chromithiocyanate, it was separated by filtration, washed with water, dried in air and analysed. [Found: SCN, 53.30; Cr 7.80. $(C_5H_5NH)_3 Cr (SCN)_6 \cdot H_2O$ requires SCN, 52.39; Cr 7.89%]. Pyridine chromithiocyanate (m.p. 113°) is practically insoluble in water and dilute acetic acid but soluble in methylethyl ketone and alcohol. Strong nitric acid and alkali decompose it.

In order to study the applicability of Beer's law, the variation in optical density of pyridine chromithiocyanate in methylethyl ketone and 95% alcohol has been measured at wave-lengths between 380 and 600 $m\mu$ by a Hilger spectrophotometer at the room temperature (28-30°). Curves have been drawn in Fig. 2.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

TABLE I

Solvent	Methyl ethyl ketone		Alcohol		Curves	
	Conc. of the compd.	λ_{max}	λ_{min}	λ_{max}		λ_{min}
M/500		420,560 $m\mu$	484 $m\mu$	411,555 $m\mu$	476 $m\mu$	D
M/1000		422,558	480	412,552	476	E
M/1500		420,557	482	410,556	475	F

α -picoline chromithiocyanate.—It is formed in liquid state when α -picoline in dil. acetic acid is added to potassium chromithiocyanate solution.

The stoichiometry of α -picoline chromithiocyanate by conductometric method comes to 3:1 indicating the formula as $(C_6H_7NH)_3 Cr (SCN)_6$ (m.p. below 35°)

β -picoline chromithiocyanate.—It is formed in the same manner as α -picoline chromithiocyanate. The formula on the basis of conductometric method is $[C_6H_7NH]_3 Cr (SCN)_6 \cdot H_2O$ (m.p. below 35°)

γ -picoline chromithiocyanate.—It was obtained in the same manner as pyridine chromithiocyanate. On the basis of conductometric curves and chemical analysis the composition of γ -picoline chromithiocyanate comes as $(C_6H_7NH)_3 Cr (SCN)_6 \cdot H_2O$ (m.p. 97°). [Found: SCN, 49.65; Cr 7.32. $C_6H_7NH_3 Cr (SCN)_6 \cdot H_2O$ requires SCN, 49.73; Cr 7.42%]. The solubility of γ -picoline chromithiocyanate in different solvents is comparable to that

of pyridine chromithiocyanate. The absorbance has been measured in a similar manner as in the case of pyridine chromithiocyanate. Curves have been drawn in Fig. 3.

FIG. 3.

TABLE II

Solvent		Methyl ethyl ketone		Alcohol		Curves
Conc. of the compound.	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\lambda_{\min}$.	Curves	$\lambda_{\max}$.	$\lambda_{\min}$.	
M/500	418, 554 $m\mu$	462 $m\mu$	A	418, 552 $m\mu$	478 $m\mu$	D
M/1000	420, 556	458	B	420, 550	480	E
M/1500	420, 560	460	C	416, 553	476	F

The variation in optical density in methylethyl ketone and the stability of γ -picoline chromithiocyanate is very similar to that of pyridine chromithiocyanate. The presence of methyl group near to the nitrogen of pyridine ring has considerably changed and affected the properties of α - and β -picoline chromithiocyanates. Thus pyridine and picolines combine with chromithiocyanate to form compounds of type $[(B)H]_2Cr(SCN)_2$ (where B-base). Further work is in progress.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

Received May 11, 1966.